

A Non-Linear Ultrasonic Method for Damage Characterization in a Shaly Sandstone

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ABSTRACT: It is a well-established fact that the ultimate failure of rocks is preceded by the initiation, growth, and coalescence of micro-cracks. A plethora of techniques have been developed over the years for the characterization of the different stages of micro-cracking in rocks, but an objective approach for monitoring damage evolution in rocks has still not been fully established. In this paper, a new non-linear ultrasonic testing approach, the Scaling Subtraction Method (SSM), has been used to evaluate its potential to detect the signatures of the mechanical changes that accompanies a rock at different levels of damage. This approach is implemented based on the hypothesis that non-linear components of ultrasonic waves have increased sensitivity to damage. Firstly, aluminium, Gosford sandstone and Lyon's sandstone were characterized and their inherent non-linearity was established using a SSM non-linear indicator θ . Then, a Gosford sandstone specimen was damaged under uniaxial compressive step-loading and ultrasonic measurements were performed at each loading step. The non-linear indicator θ was calculated as the specimens were progressively damaged, and in such a way, the efficiency of SSM technique in capturing damage signatures was evaluated. The study concluded that the elastic non-linearity in a specimen, either due to its inherent micro-structure or due to damage, can be successfully quantified using the non-linear SSM indicator (θ).

1. INTRODUCTION

Yielding of rocks at stresses well below the laboratory ultimate compressive strength (UCS) is associated with the damage induced in the rocks due to the initiation and coalescence of micro-cracks. The stress corresponding to the systematic initiation of the cracks is defined as the Crack Initiation (CI) threshold, while the stress threshold at which the accumulated cracks in the rock begin to coalesce is termed as Crack Damage (CD) (Diederichs and Martin, 2010; Ghazvinian, 2015). Characterization of these damage thresholds is vital for a precise prediction of the rock behavior during the excavation of underground structures. A number of approaches have been developed over the past years for characterizing these damage thresholds, but an objective approach for determination of an early damage (CI) evolution is still difficult at best (Nicksiar and Martin, 2012; Meyer, 2018). In this study, a non-linear ultrasonic testing

(NLUT) method has been used to evaluate its capability to detect the signatures of different stages of micro-cracking in a uniaxially loaded (shaly) Gosford sandstone specimen.

The conventional approach for evaluating the physio-mechanical response of brittle heterogeneous material consists of analyzing the stress-strain behaviors observed in standardized mechanical tests (Martin and Chandler, 1994; Eberhardt, 1998; Nicksiar and Martin, 2012). Such an approach establishes the typical macro-behavior of the testing materials by monitoring the reaction of the testing materials in response to the applied loads (Nicksiar and Martin, 2012; Moradi-Marani et al., 2014). These methods are limited in their ability to detect small-scale growth of distributed micro-cracks (Shah and Hirose, 2010); and are often not robust enough to objectively identify the different stages of damage propagation and the state of distributed micro-cracking (Van Den Abeele and Visscher, 2000). Consequently, it

is very important to develop methods that are capable of accurately tracking the stress induced growth of micro-cracks.

Non-destructive techniques (NDT) offer distinct advantage over the conventional destructive techniques, as they are capable of determining the noninvasive properties of the material while allowing easy implementation of in-place inspection of structures or materials of interest (Nogueira and Willam, 2001). Several NDT methods have been developed over the past years for damage evaluation of materials ranging from steel to rock (acoustic emission, pulse-echo, magnetic methods, electrical methods, thermography and ultrasonic methods etc.). The ultrasonic method, because of its ease of use and ability to capture the signatures of the micro-scopic changes in a material's internal structure have been used extensively to monitor continuous crack growth and damage processes (Jones, 1952; Suaris and Fernando, 1987; Sayers et al., 1987; Scott et al., 1993; Lillamand et al., 2010; Hedayat et al., 2014a-c; Ghazvinian, 2015; Hedayat and Walton, 2017; Shirole et al., 2017). Ultrasonic testing methods can be further classified into linear ultrasonic testing (LUT) methods and non-linear ultrasonic testing (NLUT) methods, based on whether the linear or non-linear component of the ultrasonic waves has been investigated. LUT is a more traditional approach for characterizing damage in material and probes the gradual changes in the linear ultrasonic wave parameters (i.e. pulse velocity, amplitude attenuation, and frequency shifts) with increasing micro-damage in a material (Hudson, 1981). The linear theory of ultrasonic (acoustic) wave propagation is based on the assumption that: (1) the pulse velocity in a medium is constant, and (2) the density and elasticity of a medium is independent of the transmitting wave amplitude (Zheng et al., 1999). Theoretically, the first assumption implies that a monochromatic ultrasonic wave will have no phase distortion as it propagates through a medium, although its amplitude might reduce due to scattering of the acoustic energy; that is why amplitude is a more sensitive parameter for capturing signatures of damage in a medium in comparison to pulse velocity (Walsh, 1966; Gowd, 1970; Shah and Chandra, 1970; Gupta, 1973; Suaris and Fernando, 1987; Shah and Hirose, 2010; Hedayat et al., 2012). Although wave attenuation is a fairly sensitive parameter for monitoring damage in a material, the quantitative changes especially in wave velocity are often insignificant and difficult to measure at low crack densities. As such, LUT methods may fail to identify low or moderate levels of damage, such as damage close to the CI threshold (Shokouhi et al., 2010). In contrast, NLUT techniques have been shown to be capable of easily detecting low levels of damage in wide spectrum of materials (Roe et al., 2007; Worden et al., 2008; Munoz et al., 2015). In the present paper, a state-

of-the-art NLUT technique, the scaling subtraction method (SSM), has been tested to assess its potential for characterizing the damage processes in Gosford sandstone (Masoumi et al., 2018). SSM has been previously used for identifying damage in concrete and composite plates, but the effectiveness of SSM technique for detecting the presence of damage in rocks has not yet been assessed. SSM uses a non-linear parameter θ , in order to characterize the damage and the associated non-linearity of the material. In the following section, a brief description of the fundamental theories related to the non-linear elastic response of rocks is provided. After this, the NLUT-SSM technique, experimental approach, results and conclusions are presented.

2. THEORY

Non-linear elastic response is a robust and illustrative characteristic in rocks, established by the fact that rocks show such behavior over many orders of magnitude of strain (Johnson and Rasolofosaon, 1996). Non-linear response in terms of quasi-static stress-strain experiments under large strains is well established; this phenomenon occurs primarily because of the “defects” in rock (cracks, grain boundaries, joints etc.). However, the existence of significant non-linear elastic response at small (dynamic) level of strains (10^{-6} to 10^{-9} ; strains due to a propagating ultrasonic wave) is a phenomenon which is less well understood.

The “Defects”, as mentioned above, are the major contributors to the non-linear response of rocks. The interfaces of these defects can be ideally bonded or fully open; but when these interfaces are in a partially clamped state, they behave in a highly non-linear manner. These interfaces generate Contact Acoustic Non-linearity (CAN) when insonified at high energy levels (Woodward et al., 2004). A conceptual model which explains the CAN is based on the concept of two springs oriented perpendicular to a crack (Figure 1); one spring is soft but non-linear $\left\{k_1 = k_0 \left(1 + \delta \varepsilon^2 + \dots\right)\right\}$ (ε is the strain amplitude) due to mechanical damage, and one is stiff (k_2) and associated with the surrounding stiff material, assuming mechanical damage is localized (Guyer and Johnson, 2009). Here, δ is the cubic anharmonic non-linear coefficient obtained by using the classical perturbation theory approach for describing wave propagation in a non-linear homogenous material (for details see Johnson et al., 2004, and, Guyer and Johnson, 2009). At low amplitudes, a longitudinal wave propagating through the crack (shown in Figure 1) will behave linearly as the soft spring at low energy will not be able to cause any wave distortion. As the amplitude of the wave increases, the soft spring will produce non-linearity in wave characteristics due to the significant effect of the higher order strain terms in the

instantaneous stiffness of the soft spring. With further increase in the amplitude, the crack, or asperities in the crack, begin to contact each other producing ultra-harmonics, i.e. CAN (Guyer and Johnson, 2009). This physical explanation of the genesis of the non-linearity in waves propagating through a medium with “defects” is consistent with the theory that dynamic non-linear behavior in solid materials is produced due to increasing wave-amplitudes, which subsequently produce amplitude-dependent non-linear effects, manifested in equations of continuity of the medium, resulting in non-linear equations of motions (Zheng et al., 1999).

Figure 1. (a) Conceptual model showing crack in a solid. (b) Mathematical model, where F_N is an oscillatory force (due to the propagating wave), and, k_1 (soft) and k_2 (stiff) are the spring constants (modified from Guyer and Johnson, 2009).

It has been demonstrated that the non-linearity explained through the traditional classical approach of perturbation theory (anharmonicity, i.e. anaharmonic interaction at micro-scale level) is not capable of quantitatively predicting observations in rocks, as rocks are said to be exhibiting non-classical non-linear behavior (Johnson et al., 2004). This behavior in rocks can be attributed to the very complex micro-structure of rock, consisting of contacts, grain boundaries, cracks, and zones between materials of different acoustic impedance, voids, residual fluid and macroscopic fractures (McCall and Guyer, 1996). Another factor contributing to the non-classical non-linear behavior is attributed to the presence of large number of hysteretic mechanical features contained in the mechanically soft bonds between the mechanically hard grains of all kinds of rocks in general (Johnson et al., 2004). McCall and Guyer (1996) developed the phenomenological Preisach and Mayergoyz (P-M) Space model of elasticity that combined hysteresis and end-

point memory into stress-strain equation of state (for details read McCall and Guyer, 1996; Ostrovsky and Johnson, 2001). The P-M model simulates the non-classical non-linear elastic behavior of a rock by a framework of mesoscopic elastic mechanical elements. The mechanical elements are modeled as springs that switch hysteretically between two configurations, open and closed, depending on the applied pressure. The mechanical elements differ from one another in how they respond to an applied external pressure pair (P_c =closing pressure; P_o =opening pressure). Hysteresis is induced in the system because the response of each mechanical element is different for a particular applied pressure pair. A physical model based on analysis of inter-grain contacts with a unified description of classical acoustic non-linearity, stress-strain hysteresis and long-time relaxation in structured media was recently proposed by Lebedev and Ostrovsky (2014).

The differences between classical non-linear and non-classical non-linear acoustic (dynamic) behavior include: a downshift of the resonant frequency, proportional to the resonance amplitude in non-classical materials; non-linear attenuation in the non-classical case versus amplitude independent attenuation in the classical case; and quadratic amplitude dependence of the third harmonic versus cubic in the classical case (Hauptert et al., 2011; Munoz et al., 2015). The implications of the non-linear classical and non-classical contributions on acoustic wave transmission and the associated material constitutive principles has been highlighted in greater depth in the work of Van-den Abeele et al. (2000) and Munoz et al. (2015).

3. SCALING SUBTRACTION METHOD

As explained in Section 2, the propagation of an ultrasonic elastic wave in an approximately classical non-linear medium is controlled by a non-linear stress-strain constitutive relationship (for more details refer to Munoz et al., 2015). For a one-dimensional longitudinal wave propagating in a classical homogenous medium, the stress-strain relationship associated with it are governed by the perturbation theory through the expansion of strain energy in powers of strain (Landau and Lifshitz, 1986; Johnson et al., 2004). As rock is a non-classical material, however, the additional contributions due to hysteresis and end-point memory also need to be accounted in the constitutive laws. Different models and equations exist to model different types of non-linearity: classical (Landau and Lifshitz, 1986), non-classical (McCall and Guyer, 1994) etc. The anharmonic (classical non-linear) and hysteretic (non-classical non-linear) contributions in the stress-strain relationship of a material disrupts the proportionality between the excitation amplitude (due to a propagating wave) and its response. Due to the disproportionate

nature of the stress-strain relationship, the linear superposition principle is violated. The SSM approach picks these unique signatures of non-linear response, which exist because of the loss of scaling relations between the driving wave amplitude and the detected time domain waveforms.

The Scaling Subtraction Method (SSM) evaluates the difference between the acquired non-linear signal ($v_{non-lin}(t)$) and a linear reference signal ($v_{ref}(t)$). The reference signal ($v_{ref}(t)$) represents the ideal linear elastic response of the same material to the same input amplitude (A), neglecting the effect of defects and damage in the material (Antonaci et al., 2010). The approach for defining the linear reference signal is based on the assumption that, when a material is insonified at sufficiently low amplitudes (A_{lin}), non-linear contribution to the response of the material is insignificant, meaning the experimentally measured recorded signal ($v_{lin}(t)$) at (A_{lin}) can be considered as the linear-elastic response of the material (Antonaci et al., 2010; Porcu et al., 2017). The linear reference signal ($v_{ref}(t)$) at a higher amplitude ($A=k \cdot A_{lin}$) is established by implementing the superposition principle (scaling the linear signal), which is valid because of the presumed linearity of the material at low excitation-amplitudes. The relationship between the response of the material at high amplitudes and the corresponding non-linear signal will be:

$$v_{ref}(t) = k \cdot v_{lin}(t) \neq v_{non-lin}(t) \quad (1)$$

The non-linear attributes (classical and non-classical non-linearity) encompassed in the dynamic response of a material can now be easily separated by subtracting the scaled reference signal from the acquired non-linear signal (Eqn. 2). The obtained signal is called the scaled subtracted (SS) signal ($v_{ss}(t)$), and is a characteristic of the non-linear features of the material only.

$$v_{ss}(t) = v_{ref}(t) - v_{non-lin}(t) \quad (2)$$

Except for noise effects, the scale subtracted signal will be negligible for non-damaged and linear materials (perfectly linear behavior), while it increases with increasing amounts of damage (Porcu et al., 2017). The non-linear content of the response can be quantified through the total SSM indicator θ . It represents the energy of the SSM signal and is calculated based on the area under the time-domain SSM signals (Bruno et al., 2009; Moradi-Marani et al., 2014):

$$\theta = \sum_{i=1}^{N-1} \left[0.5(A_{SSi} + A_{SSi+1}) \right]^2 \cdot \Delta t \quad (3)$$

Here, $N=10000$ is the number of samples that corresponds to a sampling time of $10 \mu s$ for the response of the material; A_{ss} is the amplitude of the SS signal ($v_{ss}(t)$) and Δt is the interval between two sample points. θ

calculated in present work is normalized with respect to Δt , because it is constant throughout the testing scheme.

Relative to methods that deal with detection of sub-harmonics and super-harmonics, the scaling subtraction method is simplistic and more objective. This is because the non-linear signature is derived by a simple subtraction method and without the introduction of mathematical parameters commonly involved in filtering procedures like time-window length, tapering, zero-padding etc. (Bruno et al., 2009). The other benefit of SSM lies in the fact that the amplitude of the retained non-linear signals are large enough to be easily distinguishable from the background noise (to overcome noise associated with the linear signal, a threshold of 5 mV was set for acquiring the linear signal). On the other hand, the signal-to-noise ratio is low for the analysis involving the detection of sub and super-harmonic contents, which makes it difficult to apply them objectively in detection of low-level of damage. SSM also doesn't require the transducers to be localized close to the non-linear components of the material being studied (Porcu et al., 2017).

4. EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN

4.1 Experimental Set-up

Figure 2. Schematic representation of the experimental set-up for the ultrasonic measurements. Waveform generator is capable of providing input excitation between 1-400 Volts.

The non-linear ultrasonic measurements were performed by using two identical contact type video-scan longitudinal wave transducers (V-103) from Olympus NDT with a central frequency of 1 MHz and element diameter of 13 mm. One of the transducers was used as an emitting source and the other one as a receiver (Figure 2). During the experiments, transducers were coupled to the rock specimen at its mid-span along the axial length so that the wave transmission is normal to the major principal stress direction. The transducers were coupled to the surface of the specimens using a thin layer of honey as it is widely considered to be the best coupling agent for longitudinal wave propagation (Couvreur and Thimus, 1996; Hedayat et al., 2012; 2013; 2014; Gheibi and Hedayat, 2018). Rubber bands were used to attach the sensors to the specimen. The sensor assembly and coupling process was systematized to ensure repeatability in the ultrasonic measurements.

To provide excitation to the emitting transducer, two waveform generators were used: for low voltage excitation (1-20 V), an Agilent 33500B was used, and for high voltage excitation (20-400 V), an Olympus 5077PR was used. The two waveform generators were calibrated and synced so that they output the same time-domain single cycle pulses at a frequency of 5 kHz. The amplitude of the input signals generated by the waveform generators were controlled so that they are gradually increasing so as to obtain linear and non-linear signals systematically. The output of the receiving transducer was connected to an oscilloscope (Tektronix TDS 3014C DPO) for real-time data acquisition. The transmitted signals were recorded after stable conditions were reached, and they were acquired with a sampling frequency of 1 GHz which ensured a precise signal reconstruction based on the Nyquist's theorem (Antonaci et al., 2010). A Lab-view program was written to acquire the signals from the oscilloscope to the PC in real-time. Before using the testing apparatus, its linearity was carefully demonstrated in order to negate any possible adverse effects that could modify the experimental observations. For this purpose, the emitting and receiving transducers were attached without any intermediate material media (except honey), and the SSM approach was implemented to check the linearity of the test set-up.

4.2 Material and Loading Process

In the present study, both linear (aluminum) and non-linear (mortar, Gosford sandstone, Lyon's sandstone) materials have been characterized through SSM technique. All these samples were geometrically similar and were tested in their intact (undamaged) state. Two right cylindrical specimens of Gosford sandstone, 105 mm long and 52 mm in diameter were used for studying the damage evolution, one using the conventional strain based approach and one using the SSM technique. For the conventional approach, the specimen was damaged monotonically by applying a quasi-static compressive load along its axial dimension under a constant strain rate of 1 $\mu\text{m/s}$. For the SSM approach, the specimen was damaged using step-loading, and periodically throughout the test, the strain level was held constant at each step to allow a series of ultrasonic measurements to be made.

Gosford sandstone is a unit within the massive (290m thick) Triassic Hawkesbury sandstone of the Sydney Basin on the east coast of New South Wales. X-ray diffraction analysis of Gosford sandstone showed that it is comprised of quartz (86%), illite (7%), kaolinite (6%) and anatase (1%) (Masoumi et al., 2017). Using an X-ray CT scan, the porosity of the Gosford sandstone was estimated to be approximately between 18.5% and 20% (Roshan et al., 2016; Roshan et al., 2017), and the average solid density was calculated to be 2226.5 kg/m^3 (Ord et al., 1991; Sufian and Russell, 2013). The

maximum grain size was estimated as 600 μm using the sieve analysis method (Masoumi et al., 2016). Cores of the Gosford sandstone were drilled and the specimens were surface grounded to within 0.01 mm under dry conditions using mechanized grinding.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

5.1 Intact Specimens

Figure 3. Superposition of the linear reference signal (solid red line) on the high voltage non-linear signal (dotted black line). The SSM signal is also shown (solid blue line), which is the algebraic difference between reference and non-linear signal. (a) aluminium specimen (b) Gosford sandstone specimen.

One linear intact specimen type, aluminium, and three non-linear intact specimen types, Gosford sandstone, mortar, Lyon's sandstone have been tested to establish the potential of SSM for characterization of material behavior. To ensure linear behavior of the ultrasonic system, suitable measurements on the equipment were also carried out. Specifically, the procedure which was followed for measuring the non-linearity of the four

specimens was also applied to directly coupled transducers with only honey as the intermediate medium. The reconstructed reference signal ($v_{ref}(t)$), high voltage non-linear signal ($v_{non-lin}(t)$) and the SS signal ($v_{ss}(t)$) for the aluminium and Gosford sandstone specimen are shown in Figure 3 for input excitation voltage of 400 V.

The linear and non-linear signals are fairly similar at the given excitation voltage for the aluminium specimen (Figure 3a) while there is a marked difference in these signals for Gosford sandstone (Figure 3b). The non-linear indicator (θ) was then calculated as a measure of the energy of the SSM signals (Eqn. 3). Using a similar procedure, the non-linear indicator (θ) was calculated for the equipment, a Lyon's sandstone specimen and a mortar specimen. Figure 4 illustrates the plot of θ versus the output amplitude of the transmitted signals, for all the tested materials and the equipment. The equipment (ultrasonic system) shows negligible non-linearity in comparison to the materials, which confirms that the non-linearity in the system is negligible.

Figure 4. Characterization of different materials through their non-linear signature by the application of SSM technique.

Based on Figure 4, the linear and non-linear behavior of different materials can be easily differentiated. In particular, the non-linear indicator of the aluminium specimen is insignificant when compared with the non-linear indicators of the sandstones and mortar. Figure 4 also shows non-linear dependence of θ on the output amplitude for mortar, Gosford sandstone and Lyon's sandstone. Gosford sandstone has the maximum sensitivity to the test voltage, while the sensitivity of mortar falls between that of Gosford and Lyon's sandstones. Mortar is known to be non-linear (Bruno et al, 2009). Although both Gosford and Lyon's sandstone have broadly similar mineralogical characteristics (e.g. primarily quartz), there is a marked difference in the

inherent non-linearity of the two rocks. This difference in the behavior of the two rocks can instead be attributed to the porosity of the two rocks and their cementation. Gosford sandstone is much more porous (18-20%), while Lyon's sandstone has a relatively less porosity (4-5%). Lyon's sandstone is well-sorted and has high compressive strength (UCS=190 MPa; and Elastic Modulus=45 GPa as per Thompson (1949) and Shirole et al. (2017)), whereas Gosford sandstone is a poorly cemented immature quartz sandstone (Sufian and Russel, 2013; Zhao et al., 2014). The increased presence of pore-spaces combined with weak cementation likely contribute to the high dynamic non-linearity shown by Gosford sandstone. Because Gosford sandstone exhibited the greatest degree of non-linearity, it was chosen to test the potential of the SSM method for damage detection during uniaxial loading.

5.2 Specimen under Uniaxial Compression

Figure 5. Stress-strain plot for the Gosford specimen. Plot also shows the CI and CD thresholds identified through the crack volumetric strain and instantaneous tangent modulus curves respectively (Ghazvinian, 2015).

The effectiveness of the SSM technique in tracking damage development in a specimen through the variation of the non-linear indicator (θ) is examined in this section. Before proceeding with ultrasonic testing, a Gosford specimen was damaged in a quasi-static manner under monotonic loading. Figure 5 shows the quasi-static loading curve of the Gosford specimen, which is typical of the curve produced when the ultrasonic measurements were carried out on the specimen. The curves of total volumetric strain versus percent failure strength (stress as a percentage of the UCS) and the crack volumetric strain versus percent failure strength for the Gosford sandstone are also shown. The elastic

modulus was calculated to be 14 GPa and the Poisson's ratio was 0.11. The mechanical changes produced in the Gosford specimen due to damage can be analyzed by the quasi-static loading curve. Figure 5 shows that there is a compaction stage up to about 30% of the failure strength (pore-collapse and hardening), followed by a period of linear behavior, and ultimately non-linear material softening (CD) close to the failure strength. For the specimen considered, the UCS was 39 MPa. CI was estimated to be 43-46% of the UCS, while the CD threshold was 76-78% of the UCS (Figure 5). CI and CD were calculated based on the conventional approaches in which CI is the stress corresponding to the point of inflection in the crack volumetric strain curve, while CD corresponds to the onset of relaxation in the elastic modulus of the rock as calculated through the tangent modulus curve.

Figure 6. Different curves show the variation of non-linear indicator (θ) with output voltage at different levels of damage progression. The SSM non-linear indicator show three different stages of material behavior: material hardening probably due to pore collapse (the non-linear curve decreases up to of 20%); crack initiation as the non-linear curve rises remarkably at 50% of the UCS; and material non-linear behavior due to crack propagation between 65-80% of UCS.

The SSM non-linear testing was conducted under uniaxial step-loading for a Gosford specimen which had the same damage characteristics as shown in Figure 5. For analysis of the damage progression using SSM technique, the ultrasonic measurements were performed in the time interval between one loading step and the following. Figure 6, depicts the variation of the SSM non-linear indicator (θ) versus output amplitude at different stages of loading. The curve of the SSM indicator does not show a monotonic trend. Initially, it exhibits a decrease in the non-linear signal content (yellow and red curves in Figure 6). With further increase in the load, θ progressively reverts back to the same value as that of the intact (undeformed) specimen

(deep blue line), and eventually surpasses it (purple line). With further increment in the loads, θ increases further and becomes more sensitive to the signal voltage (light blue and maroon line). At loads very close to the UCS, the θ indicator is approximately four times as large as its value for the specimen in its unloaded state.

Damage (i.e. the presence of micro-cracks) is directly related to the increment in the non-linear content of the propagating ultrasonic waves. It will be essential to examine the results from the quasi-static loading curve and associate them with the non-linear ultrasonic measurements for interpretation of the damage processes based on non-linear indicator θ . For this, Figure 7 shows the variation in non-linear indicator θ versus load level. The θ parameter in Figure 7 corresponds to the maximum output level of the transmitted signals, where a fixed input excitation of 400 V corresponds to the maximum output level.

Figure 7. Variation of the non-linear indicator θ with loading for Gosford sandstone specimen with input excitation amplitude of 400 V. The non-linear indicator θ first decreases (Stage I), then rises at a gentle rate (Stage II), and with further loading increases significantly (Stage III).

The interpretation of the non-linear ultrasonic measurements (Figure 7), can be enhanced through comparison with the observations made through the quasi-static loading curve (Figure 5). In particular, three stages can be distinguished by examining Figure 7. Initially in stage I, which corresponds to low load levels, a decrease in the non-linear signal content is observed. This is consistent with the increase in the slope of the stress-strain curve (material hardening). Studies have shown that during initial stages of compressive loading, a compaction phase is observed in rocks (Bieniawski, 1967; Bogusz and Bukowska, 2015). This stage is quite pronounced in Gosford sandstone, because it can be categorized as a loose and porous rock containing

numerous small pre-existing fractures (Brace, 1964; Wawersik and Fairhurst, 1970; Sufian and Russel, 2013). Stage I can be correlated with a rearrangement of the internal structure, with micro-structures closing down and pores collapsing, causing an increase in the stiffness of the specimen. The sealing of pre-existing pores and micro-cracks, without formation of any new micro-crack, is central to the reduction in the non-linearity of the specimen as observed in Figure 7. Further, as observed in the crack-strain plot (Figure 5), new micro-cracks are not formed approximately between 26-40% of the loading (perfectly linear-elastic behavior), which is consistent with the fairly constant non-linear indicator in the same stress regime. At approximately 40% of the loading, the non-linear indicator θ increases abruptly to approximately the same level as that of the intact specimen (Stage II). This observation is consistent with the CI threshold estimated using the crack strain curve (Figure 5). Between 44-66% of the loading, the SSM non-linearity continues to rise gradually. Although, the axial-strain versus percent loading curve is linear in this region, but the non-linearity in the radial strain curve (formation of isolated vertical cracks and reduction in radial stiffness) can explain the slight increase in non-linearity observed in stage II. Finally, an abrupt rise in the non-linear indicator occurs at about 67% of the peak load (Stage III, Figure 7), which occurs prematurely when compared to the CD threshold of 76-78% (Figure 5). At CD, trans-granular cracks are formed and they start to coalesce, which reduces the stiffness of specimen. The coalescence of the micro-cracks can be the most likely reason for the observed continuous rise in the elastic non-linearity of the specimen after 67% of the ultimate loading. The signature of increased non-linearity well before the occurrence of CD (as determined by the conventional approach) is a testament of the fact that NLUT techniques are more sensitive towards the detection of damage. The objective determination of CD also suffers from the smoothing and averaging techniques used in the conventional approaches.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The mechanical behavior of rocks is substantially influenced by internal micro-mechanical processes. An attempt has been made in this study to capture the effects of these internal changes using a non-linear ultrasonic testing technique, the scaling subtraction method. It has been shown that the elastic non-linearity in a rock specimen, either due to its inherent micro-structure or due to damage, can be successfully quantified using the SSM indicator (θ).

The SSM technique was utilized in the characterization of material's inherent non-linearity. SSM θ indicator was found to be capable of differentiating the non-linear

elastic behavior associated with a very stiff brittle sandstone (Lyon's), and a soft sandstone (Gosford). SSM also showed negligible non-linearity for a linear aluminium specimen. The method was also experimentally validated for detection of stress-induced damage signatures. It showed reasonable sensitivity in detection of three different stages associated with damage in typical rock specimens. The significance of the SSM θ indicator was found to be in its sensitivity to damage in the early stages of deformation in the Gosford sandstone specimen. In particular, the θ indicator showed appreciable change at the stress level where micro-cracks started to develop in the Gosford specimen (CI), which is a significant advantage over other techniques used for damage detection. The non-linear indicator θ was also very sensitive in detecting the formation of trans-granular cracks in the specimen (CD). In fact, it gave an early indication of it when compared with the CD calculated based on the conventional approach. In future studies, the same technique will be applied to crystalline rocks to more broadly establish its applicability for damage detection in rocks.

REFERENCES

1. Antonaci, P., Bruno, C. L. E., Gliozzi, A. S., and Scalerandi, M. (2010). Monitoring evolution of compressive damage in concrete with linear and nonlinear ultrasonic methods. *Cement and Concrete Research*, 40(7), 1106-1113.
2. Bieniawski, Z. T. (1967). Mechanism of brittle fracture of rock: part I—theory of the fracture process. *International Journal of Rock Mechanics and Mining Sciences & Geomechanics Abstracts Vol. 4, No. 4*, pp. 395-406.
3. Bogusz, A., and Bukowska, M. (2015). Stress-strain characteristics as a source of information on the destruction of rocks under the influence of load. *Journal of Sustainable Mining*, 14(1), 46-54.
4. Brace W. F. (1964). *Brittle Fracture of Rocks, State of the Earth's Crust* (W. R. Judd, Ed.) Elsevier.
5. Bruno, C. L. E., Gliozzi, A. S., Scalerandi, M., and Antonaci, P. (2009). Analysis of elastic nonlinearity using the scaling subtraction method. *Physical Review B*, 79(6), 064108.
6. Couvreur, J.F. and Thimus, J.F. (1996). The Properties of coupling agents in improving ultrasonic transmission. *International Journal of Rock Mechanics and Mining Sciences & Geomechanics Abstract*, Vol. 33, No. 4, pp. 417-424.
7. Diederichs, M. S., & Martin, C. D. (2010). Measurement of spalling parameters from laboratory testing. In *Rock mechanics and environmental engineering*. Paper presented at European Rock Mechanics Symposium (pp. 323-326).
8. Eberhardt, E. (1998). Brittle rock fracture and progressive damage in uniaxial compression. Ph.D. Thesis, Department of Geological Sciences, University of Saskatchewan, Saskatoon.
9. Ghazvinian, E. (2015). Fracture initiation and propagation in low porosity crystalline rocks: implications for excavation damage zone (EDZ) mechanics. Ph.D. Thesis, Queen's University, Ontario, Canada.
10. Gheibi, A., and Hedayat, A. (2018). Ultrasonic Investigation of granular materials subjected to compression and crushing. *Ultrasonics*.
11. Gowd, T.N. (1970). Changes in absorption of ultrasonic energy travelling through rock specimens stressed to fracture. *Phys Earth Planet Interiors* 4:43-48.

12. Gupta, I.N. (1973). Seismic velocities in rock subjected to axial loading upto shear fracture. *J. Geophys. Res.*, 78, 6938-6942.
13. Guyer, R. A., and Johnson, P. A. (2009). *Nonlinear mesoscopic elasticity: the complex behavior of rocks, soil, concrete*. John Wiley & Sons.
14. Haudert, S., Renaud, G., Riviere, J., Talmant, M., Johnson, P.A., and Laugier, P. (2011). High-accuracy acoustic detection of nonclassical component of material nonlinearity. *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* 130, 2654–2661.
15. Hedayat, A., and Walton, G. (2017). Laboratory determination of rock fracture shear stiffness using seismic wave propagation and digital image correlation. *Geotechnical Testing Journal*, 40(10), 92-106.
16. Hedayat, A., Bobet, A and Pyrak-Nolte, L. (2012). Monitoring slip initiation and propagation along frictional interfaces with seismic wave transmission. *Proceedings of the 46th US Rock Mechanics Symposium*, Chicago, June 24-27.
17. Hedayat, A., Pyrak-Nolte, L and Bobet, A. (2013). Multi-modal monitoring of slip along frictional discontinuities. *Proceedings of the 47th US Rock Mechanics Symposium*, San Francisco, June 23-26.
18. Hedayat, A., Pyrak-Nolte, L and Bobet, A. (2014a). Precursors to shear failure of rock discontinuities. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 41, 5467-5475.
19. Hedayat, A., Pyrak-Nolte, L and Bobet, A. (2014b). Detection and quantification of slip along non-uniform frictional discontinuities using digital image correlation. *Geotechnical Testing Journal*, 37 (5).
20. Hedayat, A., Pyrak-Nolte, L and Bobet, A. (2014c). Multi-modal monitoring of slip along frictional discontinuities. *Rock Mechanics and Rock Engineering*, 47(5), 1575-1587.
21. Hedayat, A., Pyrak-Nolte, L and Bobet, A. (2014d). Geophysical investigation of shear failure along cohesive-frictional rock discontinuities. *Proceedings of the 48th US Rock Mechanics Symposium*, Minnesota, June 1-4.
22. Hudson, J.A. (1981). Wave speeds and attenuation of elastic waves in material containing cracks. *Geophysical J. R. Astron. Soc.* 64:133-150.
23. Johnson P.A. and Rasolofosaon, P.N.J. (1996). Manifestation of nonlinear elasticity in rocks: convincing evidence over large frequency and strain intervals from laboratory studies. *Nonlinear Processes in Geophysics*, 3, p. 77-88.
24. Johnson, P. A., Zinszner, B., Rasolofosaon, P., Cohen-Tenoudji, F., and Van Den Abeele, K. (2004). Dynamic measurements of the nonlinear elastic parameter α in rock under varying conditions. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Solid Earth*, 109(B2).
25. Jones, R. (1952). A method of studying the formation of cracks in a material subjected to stress, *British Journal of Applied Physics*, Vol-3.
26. Landau, L. D., and Lifshitz, E. M. (1986). *Theory of elasticity*. Pergamon Press, Oxford, 155.
27. Lebedev, A. V., and Ostrovsky, L. A. (2014). A unified model of hysteresis and long-time relaxation in heterogeneous materials. *Acoustical Physics*, 60(5), 555-561.
28. Lillamand, I., Chaix, J-F., Ploix, M-A., and Garnier, V. (2010). Acoustoelastic effect in concrete material under uni-axial compressive loading, *NDT&E International* 43 655–660.
29. Martin, C.D., and Chandler, N.A. (1994). The progressive fracture of Lac du Bonnet granite. *International Journal of Rock Mechanics and Mining Sciences and Geomechanics Abstracts* 31(6):643-659.
30. Masoumi, H., Saydam, S., and Hagan, P. C. (2016). Unified size-effect law for intact rock. *International Journal of Geomechanics*, 16(2), 04015059.
31. Masoumi, H., Horne, J., and Timms, W. (2017). Establishing empirical relationships for the effects of water content on the mechanical behavior of Gosford sandstone. *Rock Mechanics and Rock Engineering*, 50(8), 2235-2242.
32. Masoumi, H., Roshan, H., Hedayat, A., and Hagan, P. C. (2018). Scale-Size Dependency of Intact Rock under Point-Load and Indirect Tensile Brazilian Testing. *International Journal of Geomechanics*, 18(3), 04018006.
33. McCall, K. R., and Guyer, R. A. (1994). Equation of state and wave propagation in hysteretic nonlinear elastic materials. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Solid Earth*, 99 (B12), 23887-23897.
34. McCall, K. R., and Guyer, R. A. (1996). A new theoretical paradigm to describe hysteresis, discrete memory and nonlinear elastic wave propagation in rock. *Nonlinear Processes in Geophysics*, 3(2), 89-101.
35. Meyer, B. J. (2018). *A New Objective Method for the Determination of Crack Initiation Stress Using Acoustic Emission Data* (M.S dissertation, Colorado School of Mines, Arthur Lakes Library).
36. Moradi-Marani, F., Rivard, R., Lamarche, C.P., and Kodjo, S.A. (2014). Evaluating the damage in reinforced concrete slabs under bending test with the energy of ultrasonic waves. *Construction and Building Materials* (73) 663–673.
37. Munoz, R., Rus, G., Bochud, N., Barnard, D. J., Melchor, J., Ruano, J. C., and Bond, L. J. (2015). Nonlinear ultrasonic for early damage detection. In *emerging design solutions in structural health monitoring systems* (pp. 171-206). IGI Global.
38. Nicksiar, M. and Martin, C.D. (2012). Evaluation of methods for determining crack initiation in compression tests on low-porosity rocks. *Rock Mechanics and Rock Engineering* 45(4):607-617.
39. Nogueira, C.L. and Willam, K.J. (2001). Ultrasonic testing of damage in concrete under uniaxial compression. *ACI Materials Journal*, V. 98, No. 3.
40. Ord, A., Vardoulakis, I., and Kajewski, R. (1991). Shear band formation in Gosford sandstone. In *International journal of rock mechanics and mining sciences & geomechanics abstracts*, Vol. 28, No. 5, pp. 397-409.
41. Ostrovsky, L. A., & Johnson, P. A. (2001). Dynamic nonlinear elasticity in geomaterials. *Rivista del nuovo cemento*, 24(7), 1-46.
42. Porcu, M. C., Pieczonka, L., Frau, A., Staszewski, W. J., and Aymerich, F. (2017). Assessing the scaling subtraction method for impact damage detection in composite plates. *Journal of Nondestructive Evaluation*, 36(2), 33.
43. Roe, S.E., Woodward, C., and Cramer, M.J. (2007). Nonlinear ultrasonic testing on a laboratory concrete bridge deck. *Rev. Quant. Non-destruct. Eval.* 26:1429–34.
44. Roshan, H., Sari, M., Arandiyani, H., Hu, Y., Mostaghimi, P., Sarmadivaleh, M., and Regenauer-Lieb, K. (2016). Total Porosity of Tight Rocks: A Welcome to the Heat Transfer Technique. *Energy & Fuels*, 30(12), 10072-10079.
45. Roshan, H., Masoumi, H., Zhang, Y., Al-Yaseri, A. Z., Iglauer, S., Lebedev, M., and Sarmadivaleh, M. (2017). Microstructural effects on mechanical properties of shaly sandstone. *Journal of Geotechnical and Geoenvironmental Engineering*, 144(2), 06017019.
46. Sayers, C.M., J.G. Munster and M.S. King. (1990). Stress-Induced Ultrasonic Anisotropy in Barea Sandstone, *International Journal of Rock Mechanics and Mining Sciences & Geomechanics Abstracts*, Vol. 27, 429-436.
47. Scott Jr, T.E., Q., Ma and J.C. Roegiers. (1993). Acoustic velocity changes during shear enhanced compaction of sandstone. *International Journal of Rock Mechanics and Mining Sciences & Geomechanics Abstracts*, 30(7): 763-769.
48. Shah, A.A. and Hirose, S. (2010). Non-linear ultrasonic investigation of concrete damaged under uniaxial compression step loading. *Journal of Materials in Civil Engineering*, Vol. 22, No. 5.
49. Shah, S. P., and Chandra, S. (1970). Mechanical behavior of concrete examined by ultrasonic measurements. *Journal of Materials*, V. 5, No. 3, pp. 550-563.

50. Shirole, D., Hedayat, A., and Walton, G. (2017). Active ultrasonic monitoring of rocks under uniaxial compression. 51st US Rock Mechanics/Geomechanics Symposium. American Rock Mechanics Association.
51. Shokouhi, P., Zoega, A. and Wiggenhauser, H. (2010). Nondestructive investigation of stress-induced damage in concrete. *Advances in Civil Engineering* Volume 2010, Article ID 740189.
52. Suaris, W., and Fernando, V., (1987). Ultrasonic pulse attenuation as a measure of damage growth during cyclic loading of concrete. *ACI Materials Journal*, V. 84, No. 3, pp. 185-193.
53. Sufian, A., and Russell, A. R. (2013). Microstructural pore changes and energy dissipation in Gosford sandstone during pre-failure loading using X-ray CT. *International Journal of Rock Mechanics and Mining Sciences*, 57, 119-131.
54. Thompson, W. O. (1949). Lyons sandstone of Colorado Front Range. *AAPG Bulletin*, 33(1), 52-72.
55. Van Den Abeele, K., & De Visscher, J. (2000). Damage assessment in reinforced concrete using spectral and temporal nonlinear vibration techniques. *Cement and concrete research*, 30(9), 1453-1464.
56. Van Den Abeele, K., Johnson, P.A., and Sutin, A. (2000). NEWS technique to discern material damage, Part I: NWMS (Nonlinear Wave Modulation Spectroscopy). *Research in Nondestructive Evaluation*, 12, 17-30.
57. Walsh, J. B. (1966). Seismic wave attenuation in rock due to friction. *J. Geophys. Res.*, 71, 2591-2599.
58. Wawersik, W. R., and Fairhurst, C. (1970). A study of brittle rock fracture in laboratory compression experiments. *International Journal of Rock Mechanics and Mining Sciences & Geomechanics Abstracts*, Vol. 7, No. 5, pp. 561-575. Pergamon.
59. Woodward, C., White, K. R., Jauregui, D. V., and Stauffer, J. (2004). Nonlinear ultrasonic evaluation of concrete microcracking. In *AIP Conference Proceedings* Vol. 700, No. 1, pp. 1022-1026.
60. Worden, K., Farrar, C. R., Haywood, J., & Todd, M. (2008). A review of nonlinear dynamics applications to structural health monitoring. *Structural Control and Health Monitoring*, 15(4), 540-567.
61. Zhao, G. F., Russell, A. R., Zhao, X., and Khalili, N. (2014). Strain rate dependency of uniaxial tensile strength in Gosford sandstone by the Distinct Lattice Spring Model with X-ray micro CT. *International Journal of Solids and Structures*, 51(7-8), 1587-1600.
62. Zheng, Y., Maev, R., and Solodov, I. (1999). Nonlinear acoustic applications for material characterization: A review. *Canadian Journal of Physics*, 77(12), 927-967.